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NEWER INSIGHTS INTO THE PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF *DATURA STRAMONIUM* LINN.: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Datura stramonium is a widespread growing plant commonly known as Angel's trumpet and it belongs to the family Solanaceae. The plant comprises bioactive constituents like scopolamine, hyosciamine, tropane alkaloids, tannin, proteins and carbohydrates. It has hallucinogenic effects as well as medicinal properties. Traditionally it is used in cough, fever, asthma and also in skin disorder. The plant has extensive pharmacological effect mainly analgesic in action. A substantial evaluation is contributory in scientific assessment of the medicinal properties of the plant. The ethnomedicinal, phytochemical as well as toxicological works upon *Datura stramonium* gives a better understanding of the particular plant. The present paper highlights upon the various properties of *Datura stramonium* respectively.

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INTRODUCTION

Datura stramonium is mostly known as Angel's trumpet, Locoweed, Jimson weed or Datura, it belongs to family Solanaceae. The plant rises to the height of about 60-120 cm or more, they are pubescent and branched plant. The leaves dimensions are 8-17x4-13cm, sinuately dentate, minutely puberulose and ovate. The flowers are trumpet-shaped, white to creamy or violet and 6 to 9 cm long [1]. Commonly found in temperate and subtropical region [2]. Traditionally the plant is used to treat various diseases and there is a constant search for the medicinal value of plant. *Datura stramonium* has both the toxic effects and medicinal uses [3]. Since inception of life humans beings use plant for different purposes like food and medicine. Still today a large number of people use different plant for different disease treatments. *Datura stramonium* has most important medicinal use. From the ethnomedicinal point of view it has an important medicinal value throughout the world. The leaves and seeds are used in different treatment regime. The leaves of *Datura stramonium* when mixed with mustard oil it helps in treating skin disorders. The extract of flower petals is used in ear pain. Seeds are used in fever, cough, asthma and as purgatives. Seeds are also used intoxicants for its narcotic action [4]. In folklore medicine this plant were used because of its analgesic effects in the "Old world" [5]. *Datura stramonium* comprises of different types of phytochemicals including Tannins, Saponins, Alkaloids, Glycoside Flavonoids Steroids and Phenols [6]. The bioactive components present in branches and leaves extracts consists of high anti-microbial and anti-fungal activities [7].

Phytochemistry of *Datura stramonium*

Nearly more than sixty-four tropane alkaloids have been detected from *D. stramonium*. Two new tropane alkaloids, 7-epoxynortropine, 3-phenylacetoxy-6, and 7-hydroxyapoptropine were tentatively identified. The alkaloids 3-(hydroxyacetoxy) tropane, scopoline, 3-hydroxy-6-(2-methylbutyryloxy) tropane, 3,7-dihydroxy-6-tigloyloxytropane, 3 α -tigloyloxy-6-hydroxytropane 3-tigloyloxy-6-propionyloxytropane, 3-phenylacetoxy-6-hydroxytropane, aponorscopolamine, 3-phenylacetoxy-6,7-epoxytropane, 3 α ,6 α -ditigloyloxytropane and 7-hydroxyhyoscyamine are reported for the first time for this particular species [8]. The toxins in *Datura* are tropane belladonna alkaloids, which consists of strong anticholinergic effects. These alkaloids include: hyoscyine (roots); atropine (d,l-hyoscyamine) hyoscyamine (leaves, roots, seeds), and scopolamine (l-hyoscyine), as well as protein and sitosterol [9,10]. It is reported that hyoscyamine is the predominant alkaloid in DS from the (11,12). Thorn apple leaves contains 0.2%-0.45% of total alkaloids, seeds approximately 0.2% (11). The tropane alkaloid contain a methylated nitrogen atom (N-CH₃) and include the anticholinergic drugs, atropine, hyoscyamine, and scopolamine as well as the narcotic cocaine (13).

Ethnomedicinal uses

When the leaves of *Datura stramonium* mixed with mustard oil then it is useful in skin disorders. Juice of flower petals is used in ear pain and seeds are used as purgative, in cough, fever and asthma. Seeds are smoked due to its narcotic action [14]. Leaf paste and extract is externally used for injuries, wounds, bleedings and pains. Seeds in small quantity used for asthma and tonsil problems. The extract of leaves is also used for baldness [15]. Leaves used externally for management of pains [16]. *Datura stramonium* plant frequently used as antiparasitics and repellents [17]. Fruit oil is used for body pain [18]. Leaf or whole plant is Antiinflammatory and antispasmodic [19]. Green leaves are applied for the softening of the boils. Juice of the fruit is applied to scalp for falling hairs and as antidandruff. Juice of the flower is used in earache. One drop is poured in the ear at night [20]. Paste of leaves is topically applied for skin diseases [21]. Dried leaves and seeds are used as Anticholinergic and sedative [22]. Seeds are used to make somebody unconscious [23]. Traditionally it is used for cure of Rheumatism. cure of the pain [24]. 75 gm rhizomes of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), 100 gm of garlic (*Allium sativum*) and 85 gm of onions (*Allium cepa*) are macerated together to extract the juice. To the juice is added 86 gm atosh (root of an unidentified plant) and an equal amount of darmuz (arsenic), mudra shankar (unidentified chemical, possibly a chromium salt) and camphor. One powdered seed of *Datura stramonium* is added to the mixture along with 400 gm of oil from seeds of *Brassica campestris*. The whole amount is boiled thoroughly, slightly cooled and applied to places where there is rheumatic pain. This is done 2-3 times daily till pain is cured.

Medicinal Uses

D. stramonium is used frequently as an antiasthmatic treatment [25,26,27]. The widely reported medicinal uses include the use of the dried leaves of the plant as an anti-asthmatic agent [28,29,30]. As the cure for the asthma mixture of the leaves and seeds is taken orally as a decoction or smoke. [31]. Aqueous extract of the seeds are reported to be used in the treatment of gastric pains and indigestion [32]. Furthermore, this plant as herbal remedy is also frequently given to pregnant mother with asthmatic complaints. It is used as a medicinal, psychotropic, sacred & antispasmodic [33]. It is used for asthma, burns, ulcers, sinus infection, headaches, sores (Mitchell & MH Ahmad, 2006). DS is used recreationally for its central anticholinergic effects and is made easily into an extract by boiling the crushed seeds. The extract has rapid onset of effects and may be useful for treatment of organophosphate poisoning (Theodore et al., 2004). DS is a medicinal plant with antinociceptive (Abdollahi et al., 2003) antioxidant (Couladis et al., 2003), hypolipidemic (Resekh et al., 2001), anti-inflammatory, anti-rheumatoid (Tariq et al., 1989), and hypoglycemic properties (Gharaibeh et al., 1988).

Pharmacological properties

D. stramonium seed extract has an analgesic effect on both acute & chronic pain which were produced by hot plate and formalin tests. It is likely that, this effect can be attributed to the alkaloid which interact with opioid system (Khalili et al., 2004). The whole plant is toxic, particularly the foliage & seeds. The anticholinergic syndrome results from the inhibition of central and peripheral muscarinic neurotransmission. The patient presents with dry skin and mucosa, flushing, accommodation that causes blurred vision and photophobia, altered mental status, hyperpyrexia, sinus tachycardia, urinary retention, myoclonic jerking. Other symptoms may include ataxia, impaired short-term memory, disorientation, confusion, hallucinations, psychosis, agitated delirium, seizures, coma, respiratory failure and cardiovascular collapse (Alberto et al., 2001). Its anticholinergic compounds are likely to produce delirium and stupor but rarely cause deep coma (Ohernodorfer et al., 2002). The ethanolic extracts obtained from both leaf and seed in the thorn apple were investigated for acaricidal, repellent and oviposition deterrent properties against adult two-spotted spider mites (*Tetranychus urticae* Koch) under laboratory conditions. Leaf & seed extracts, which were applied in 167,250 and 145,750 mg/l concentrations, respectively caused 98% and 25 % mortality among spider mite adults after 48 h (Nabi et al., 2009). Exposure of the foetus to this plant when a mother uses it for asthma, will cause a continuous release of Ach, resulting in the desensitizing of nicotinic receptors, this could ultimately result in permanent damage to the foetus (Pretorius and Marx, 2006). The main effects of jimsonweed seeds were: decreased body weight gain, serum alkaline phosphatase and blood urea nitrogen. Female rats showed more marked responses to jimson weed seed than did males. In addition to the effects seen in both sexes, the females developed decreased serum total protein and cholesterol, and increase serum glutamic, pyruvic transaminase and chloride, red blood cell count, haemoglobin concentration and packed red cell volume (Dugan et al., 1989). An extract prepared from the seeds of the DS possess activity typical of a protein haemagglutinin or lectin. The extract is capable of agglutinating erythrocytes from several species, and is non-specific with regard to human ABO blood groups (Kalpatrick et al., 1978). Laboratory monitoring of changes in some blood parameters in horses intoxicated with jimsonweed was carried out. It was established that the intoxication was accompanied by hyperchromaemic, erythrocytosis, leukocytosis, neutrophilia and regenerative shift, lymphocytopenia, aneosinophilia, increased haematocrit values and low erythrocyte sedimentation rate (Binev et al., 2006). All parts of the plant are toxic but the highest amount of the alkaloids is contained in ripe seeds (Chang et al., 1999; De Frates, 2005). They act as competitive antagonist of acetylcholine at peripheral and central muscarinic receptors sites (Dugan et al., 1989). Poisoning results in widespread paralysis of parasympathetic innervated organs (Friedman et al., 1989). *Datura* aqueous leaf extract-induced cytotoxicity & oxidative stress in human cancer cell lines (Ahmad, 2009). Severe toxicity has been associated with coma and seizures, although death is rare (Dewitt et al., 1997).

CONCLUSION

Studies indicated that *Datura stramonium* is a wild plant having various medicinal and pharmacological properties. Phytochemical of the plant are alkaloids, atropine, scopolamine, tannin, saponine, glycosides, phenol, sterols, lignins, fats, carbohydrates and proteins. Extract with water and ethanol contains saponine, steroids, alkaloids and glycosides. Alkaloids, tannins, carbohydrates and proteins are used in medicines due to its analgesic and antiasthmatic activities. Atropine used in treatment of Parkinson's disease, peptic ulcers, diarrhea and bronchial asthma. Water extract of *D. stramonium* show insecticidal while ethanol extract show good anti-microbial activities. Traditionally leaves past and extracts are externally used for injuries, wounds, bleeding and pain. Juice of flower petals is used in ear pain and seeds are used as purgative, in cough, fever and asthma.

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